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Abstract

This document presents the setup for the different channels used by EVERSE for its project website, newsletter and social media. Chapter 1 gives a short introduction; Chapter 2 outlines the development, updating and content creation for the project website. In Chapter 3 the newsletter and its distribution are discussed. Finally, Chapter 4 looks at the handling of engagement on social media platforms.

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
0.1	27.08.2024	First draft by CERN	Sanje Fenkart (CERN)
0.2	29.08.2024	First revision, more precise and brief version	Graeme Stewart (CERN)
0.3	30.08.2024	More elaborate executive summary; added information for social. Media	Sanje Fenkart (CERN)
1.0	30.08.2024	Final version	Sanje Fenkart (CERN)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the setup planned for the project website development, a quarterly newsletter and a social media presence. Each chapter presents the content and handling of each channel. It shows how each one is used either as a separate outreach method and how they can be combined. The document also provides a little on possible content to report on; content is dynamic and will hence be decided by actuality.

1 Introduction

In order to reach and engage with a broader audience, the EVERSE project has set a “Dissemination & Exploitation plan” (see deliverable D6.3). In this scope several channels for outreach activities have been identified:

- ▶ The project’s webpage
- ▶ A newsletter
- ▶ Different social media platforms.

All the above-mentioned channels will be used to report on the latest news from the EVERSE project as well as being a means of staying in touch with subscribers and participants of the EVERSE Network. The following chapters describe each channel.

2 Project webpage

The project's webpage (<https://everse.software>) had its initial setup in November 2023, when the project itself was still in preparation; the first fully working version was published on 1st March, 2024.

2.1 Webpage building & development

This webpage is built using the *Hugo* engine that generates static websites from code directly. All kinds of themes and distribution can be used, in this case *blowfish* provides the general theme outline. The base code for running and adapting the webpage is stored on the dedicated GitHub repository of the project (<https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware.github.io>).

While members (mostly lead and workpackage leads) can manipulate the content and structure of the webpage or individual subpages, the main responsibility for coordinating updates and building is placed with CERN. New content can be news items (accounting for newsletter input too, see section 3), rewrites of existing content, or a new (sub-)section according to project activity.

2.2 Structure & content

Currently, the website features six main pages in addition to the landing page, with some of them holding subpages:

- ▶ About
 - ▶ Objectives
 - ▶ Consortium
 - ▶ Scientific Advisory Board
 - ▶ Workpackage Overview
 - ▶ WP1 – Network
 - ▶ WP2 – Best Practices
 - ▶ WP3 – Tools and Services
 - ▶ WP4 – Pilots and drivers
 - ▶ WP5 – Capacity and recognition
 - ▶ WP6 – Project Management
- ▶ Services
 - ▶ RSQkit
- ▶ Training
 - ▶ Training Events
- ▶ Resources
 - ▶ Presentations
 - ▶ Visual Identity
 - ▶ Promotions
- ▶ Participate
 - ▶ How to join
- ▶ News

Currently under construction are a dedicated *Network* page, a more refined representation of the consortium partners and key people of the project (management team and work package leaders).

Future content will consist of news reports and items, as well as the implementation of the newsletter articles. As the project develops the webpages will be kept up-to-date with all latest information relevant to visitors, contributors, subscribers and partners.

3 Newsletter

For a more concentrated selection of news distribution, the EVERSE project will have a newsletter that is sent out to subscribers via email. As with the project webpage, CERN and WP1 oversee the newsletter.

3.1 Management

While CERN is in charge of creating the content for the newsletter, the distribution itself is planned to be managed by a provider that offers dedicated email marketing. Currently under consideration for such a platform are MailerLite, MailChimp or Spotler.

EVERSE news can, in general, be published at any time on the webpage. The newsletter will be a quarterly curation of the news as well as special articles for each edition. The frequency will be four times per year we then estimate of 10 newsletter (see table 1 below).

Subscriber data, i.e. personal information will be handled according to the EU's GDPR and only used for the distribution of the newsletter.

Quarter	Edition	Remarks
Q3/4 2024	1	First edition, merges two quarters
Q1 2025	2	
Q2 2025	3	
Q3 2025	4	
Q4 2025	5	
Q1 2026	6	
Q2 2026	7	
Q3 2026	8	
Q4 2026	9	
Q1/2 2027	10	Final edition, project documentation, merges two quarters
Total	10	

Table 1. Overview on planned number and frequency of newsletters.

3.2 Content

Items in the newsletter will depend on the advances of the project. As EVERSE aims to be present at conferences, workshops etc. announcements and meeting reports will be part of the news. Additionally, interviews, articles on software handling, current topics of research software development and related fields can be featured.

4 Social media

Social media networks are a vital part of the dissemination plans for organisations, companies, institutes, projects and collaborations. To make itself visible, EVERSE will promote itself on social media platforms in order to:

- ▶ Attract potential members for the Network
- ▶ Inform followers about the newsletter
- ▶ Have a general presence and report on its advances.

4.1 Platforms & audience

Currently EVERSE is present on classical social media platforms such as X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn. As the project targets research software engineers (RSEs), accounts on FOSStodon (a Mastodon instance dedicated to free open source software) and GitHub, with especially the latter being a popular source of information and code on the RSE communities. And being part of the European Commission's open data policy EVERSE also has a presence on Zenodo – an open repository for outputs (such as papers and reports) generated by projects in Horizon Europe.

Platform	Account Name	Followers (as of 28.08.2024)	Link
LinkedIn	EOSC-EVERSE	104	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-everse/
X/Twitter	EVERSE (@eosc_everse)	37	https://x.com/eosc_everse
FOSStodon	EOSC EVERSE (eosc_everse)	14	https://mastodon.social/@eosc_everse@fosstodon.org
GitHub	EVERSE	14	https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware
Zenodo	EVERSE	No follower count	https://zenodo.org/communities/everse/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Table 2. Overview of EVERSE social media handles.

As of now (28.08.2024) EVERSE has had modest activity on all platforms as the project is only now starting to establish its presence.

To easier handle multiple accounts and plan posts ahead, schedule managers such as <https://buffer.com> can be used to maintain a steady presence.

4.1.1 Audience assessment

In order to prepare a more tailored social media strategy a small assessment on social media habits of members of the CERN EP-SFT (software for experiments) group has been done. They can be taken as representatives for the target audience. For this a Mentimeter presentation was made to ask about the used platforms, most used platforms, content interests and where the members look for content about or related to research software development. 27 people participated in the survey.

Summary

The most used platform overall was LinkedIn, while Mastodon/FOSStodon are not used at all. While many use social media to also look for research topic on platforms like Instagram, Twitter and LinkedIn, they mostly use it for other contents (not specified). For research software content more than half resorts to other platforms such as YouTube, reddit and GitHub (and others).

4.2 Content & strategy

For a strong social media strategy regular posting is crucial. The current aim is to have 2-3 posts per week (Mon, Thu, maybe Sat) with varying content. When a newsletter comes up, an “new-issue” post can be created. Content for the newsletter and social media can be complementary: the item from the newsletter can be individually featured or if an article was already posted (with a successful traction) it can be included into the next newsletter issue as a highlight.

Current access to social media for EVERSE is held by: Sanje Fenkart, Nikos Pechlivanis, Fotis Psomopoulos.